

THE COURSE OF SUBCLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM AND OBESITY IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Relevance of the topic: currently, obesity is one of the most common problems in the world, and along with obesity, the course of other diseases is also aggravated. So, let's talk about the processes that occur in women of reproductive age in subclinical hypothyroidism and obesity.

Keywords: subclinical hypothyroidism, reproductive age, obesity.

Obesity is accompanied by metabolic changes in the body and occurs in 12% of women of reproductive age. Subclinical hypothyroidism is characterized by a thyroxine level of 4.07-10.1 mIU / ml when determined by laboratory tests and is usually asymptomatic. However, symptoms of manifest hypothyroidism are now being detected even in subclinical hypothyroidism. It has been found that the course of obesity and subclinical hypothyroidism leads to infertility in women of reproductive age. The development of obesity in hypothyroidism occurs due to a decrease in general metabolism. In hypothyroidism, the need for oxygen in tissues decreases by 35-40%, thermogenesis and energy consumption and utilization decrease. Glucosamine glycan is a non-sulfated group of hyaluronic acid, and in hypothyroidism it is this substance that accumulates in excess in the skin, kidneys and myocardium. Its hygroscopic properties allow it to increase by a thousand times its own mass. In addition, an increase in the amount of total cholesterol is a characteristic feature of subclinical hypothyroidism. It has also been established that TSH receptors in adipocytes affect adipogenesis. In obesity, an increase in the hormone leptin is observed, and this, of course, causes an increase in TSH. Leptin physiologically serves to convey information about the sufficiency of adipose tissue, the feeling of satiety, and energy homeostasis to the central nervous system. Leptin causes changes in the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis in obese women, and the increase in leptin itself increases the level of TSH. An increase in the level of TSH causes various changes in the menstrual cycle in women of reproductive age. Thus, obesity is not only the cause of all hormonal changes, but also causes a number of psychological and social problems, and cannot but affect the reproductive function of women. However, it should be noted that in women with hypothyroidism, the main body mass is not fat, but rather excess water. Accordingly, the results of the studies determined showed that as a result of treatment with l-thyroxine, the decrease in body mass or the degree of obesity in women with this

disease did not change even after 1 year of treatment. However, from a physiological point of view, it is clearly justified to observe an increase in body mass and impaired reproductive function in the subclinical course of hypothyroidism.

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